

BANK CIMB NIAGA RESEARCH MAPPING: A VOSVIEWER-BASED BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS AND LIBRARY RESEARCH APPROACH

Wasilatur Rohimah

Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, Indonesia

Corresponding author: wasilaturrohimah@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the development of research around CIMB Niaga Islamic and Conventional Bank. The research was conducted from 2011 to 2022, by searching national journals indexed by Sinta via the Garuda website, with the keyword "CIMB Niaga". Based on the search results, there were 99 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a Library Research study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to CIMB Niaga Bank is divided into 8 clusters and 116 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a Library Research study, there are 8 main themes related to CIMB Niaga Islamic and Conventional Bank.

Keywords: *CIMB Niaga Islamic and Conventional Bank; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research*

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is a country with a majority Muslim population. This can be an extraordinary opportunity for economic development, especially in the sharia financial sector. Because of this, the development of sharia banking in Indonesia is increasing. The growth of a country's financial sector becomes the basis for intermediation between Muslim communities and the development of sharia banking. This growth can be seen from one of the banks ranked in the top 5 in Indonesia, namely Bank Niaga which opened its wings by establishing Bank Niaga Syariah.

Bank Commerce International Merchant Bankers (CIMB) Niaga was founded on September 26 1995. Initially, PT Bank Niaga only focused on building core values and professionalism in the banking sector. CIMB Niaga is the first local bank to have Automatic Teller Machine (ATM) services in Indonesia. Then on July 22 2022, this company established CIMB Niaga Syariah. This Sharia Bank was established in response to the growth of sharia banking in Indonesia and to increase customer interest in banking transactions based on sharia law (2021 financial report). PT Bank

Niaga Syariah has products offered to the public, including: collection, distribution, financing, and provision of service products such as kafalah, qardh, and ijarah.

In previous research, conventional CIMB Niaga Bank has continued to experience positive growth in recent years. In 2020, this bank managed to record a profit of IDR 2.29 trillion, an increase of around 6.8% compared to the previous year. The total assets of this bank also continue to increase and reached IDR 270.54 trillion at the end of 2020. Conventional CIMB Niaga Bank also continues to expand its reach by opening several new branches throughout Indonesia. At the end of 2020, this bank had a total of 648 branches throughout Indonesia. CIMB Niaga Syariah Bank has also experienced positive growth in recent years. In 2020, this bank managed to record a profit of IDR 156.7 billion, an increase of around 6.1% compared to the previous year. The total assets of this bank also continue to increase and reached IDR 19.8 trillion at the end of 2020. Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah continues to expand its branch network by opening several new branches throughout Indonesia. At the end of 2020, this bank had a total of 83 branches throughout Indonesia. Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah also continues to develop its products and services to meet customer needs. Some of the products offered include savings, deposits, financing and sharia credit cards. Apart from that, this bank also continues to improve service quality by providing better and more easily accessible services to its customers.

The discussion regarding Bank CIMB Niaga has been widely studied by previous studies. According to the Garuda website (Gar b a Digital Reference), around 111 researchers used the Bank CIMB Niaga case study. However, there are still only 9 studies that specifically discuss Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah, which is a very small number. This shows that research regarding Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah needs to be studied more deeply for further research. The aim of this research is to determine the map of research developments regarding Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah and Conventional. This research will be different from other research because apart from the fact that there are still few studies discussing Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah, there has been no research discussing the development of research on Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah using the VOSviewer bibliometric method and Library Research.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

PT Bank Niaga Tbk. is a bank that was founded around 27 years ago. CIMB Niaga Bank is the first bank to offer ATM services to its customers. CIMB Niaga is a national private bank that is always optimistic in its development and ready to face competition between banks in the future. Therefore, PT Bank Niaga Tbk. trying to increase competitive advantage which is expected to provide quality products and services for customers.

Bibliometric studies are the application of statistical and mathematical methods to analyze scientific journals and other writings. This bibliometric study is used for literature related to measurement. Bibliometrics is also used to evaluate literature, ranging from authorship, research topics, to scientific developments, with evaluative results that can be used as considerations in decision making.

VOSViewer is a computer program used to visualize bibliometric maps that include journals, authors, titles, publications, etc. In addition, the VOSViewer program also has the ability to map types of bibliometric analysis, generate a database of primary bibliographies, and can also perform advanced visualization using visual zoom. This tool can provide special information regarding bibliometric graphic maps to make it easier to interpret a network or correlation in a literature citation.

Library Research study is a systematic and reproducible research method for identifying, evaluating and systematically scientific literature written by researchers. The aim of this method is, among other things, to analyze existing research on the topic of discussion to be researched and find gaps for further research. Library Researchs are divided into 3 parts: narrative review, quantitative review, and qualitative review.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The object of the research is Bank CIMB Niaga. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about CIMB Niaga Syariah and Conventional Banks originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword " Bank CIMB Niaga " for the entire year (2011-2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on Library Research studies.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Bank CIMB Niaga Sharia and Conventional

Search results for scientific publications regarding Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah and Conventional during the period 2011 to 2022 show that the number of studies discussing this topic is still low. From publication data in the form of articles obtained from accredited national journals, there are only 12 articles regarding Bank CIMB

Niaga Syariah and Conventional. This means that the average scientific publication regarding Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah and Conventional is only 8 articles per year.

Table 1. Publication data regarding Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah and Conventional

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of publications
2011	2	2015	12	2019	10
2012	5	2016	11	2020	12
2013	9	2017	8	2021	8
2014	8	2018	7	2022	7
Total 99					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 201 6.

There are 10 institutions/affiliates that publish the most research articles regarding Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah and Conventional. According to the table, the FEB Student Scientific Journal is the journal publishing institution that publishes the most research results regarding Bank CIMB Niaga Sharia and Conventional, with a total of 8 publications. Based on data obtained from the Garuda website (Garda Reference Digital), each article author only writes one article. just.

Table 2. Affiliation/institution of journal publishers regarding Bank CIMB Niaga Sharia and Conventional

institution name	Number of Publications
FEB Student Scientific Journal, Brawijaya University, Malang	8
Journal of Business Management and Entrepreneurship, Tarumanegara University	5
EMBA Journal: Journal of Economic, Management, Business and Accounting Research, Sam Ratulangi University	4
Collection of Law Faculty Student Journals, PREMISE LAW JOURNAL	3
Student Online Journal (JOM) in the field of Social and Political Sciences (Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Riau University), METHODIKA: Journal of Informatics Engineering and Information Systems, (Muhammadiyah University of Tangerang), Kertha Semaya: Journal of Legal Sciences (Udayana University Faculty of Law), Journal of Islamic Economics (Prof Dr Hamka Muhammadiyah University), Journal of Information Technology and Telematics (Stikubank University)	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 201 6.

The next table contains the author's data regarding CIMB Niaga Syariah and Conventional Banks obtained from the Garuda website (Garuda Reference Digital). Each author only writes one published article.

Table 3. CIMB Niaga Syariah and Conventional Bank researchers

Writer's name	Institution Name
Siregar, Pani Akhiruddin; Sutarman, Iskandarini, Afrizal	UIN North Sumatra
Efriyenty, Dian	UIN Gunung Djati Bandung
Awaluddin Aenun, Wardhani, Rulanti Susi, Murtiadi	UIN Alauddin Makassar
Susianti, Nurul	UIN Mataram
Afriyeni, Khaira Ainil Putri, Endang	Padang State Polytechnic
Endi Yanto Frianto, Hendro; Pandia	Jakarta State Polytechnic
Janrosi, Viola Syukrina E	Batam State Polytechnic
Concerned, Oliviani Rizki Arisanti; Concerned	Semarang State Polytechnic
Elsa Andriyani Herni Widanarti, Kashadi; Wahyudi Fransiska Lucyana, Sugeng; Yasin, Ubudia Hiliyaly Chairunnisa, Abdul Qoyyim; Korn, Henry Alphonse	Diponegoro University
Permana, Imade Dedy Priyanto, Eky Putra Wakyu; Parimandana, Ida Bagus Putra Atmadja; I Wayan Agus Sima; Irmawati, IGAP Grace Sally	Udayana University
Dewani, Shinta Laura; Sisbintari, Ika; Defintasari, Arum; Hanum, Arif Hoetoro; Aulia; Audiyanto, Dickxie; Kinowati, Fita Ria; Mijati, Rini Safitri; Noer; Khudin, Saniy Desu Novania; Roe	Brawijaya University
Tommy Linda M, Parengkuan, Tawurisi; Saepul, Diansyah, Tatang; Pangalila Parengkuan, Sepang, Jantje Teddy; Vinda, Warikkie Tiara Intan; Ratag Benny S.; Wardoyo, Pingkan, Gustaaf AE; Lampus; Alum Peggy A.; Pangemanan, Franklin Jethro, Hendra N.; Mekel	Sam Ratulangi University
Christian, Mahmud Siregar; Suhaidi Suhaidi; Bismar Nasution; John Bert; Akbar, Reza Kurnia; Sukarja, Ruth Siallagan; Bismar Nasution; Det	University of Northern Sumatra
Prismadana, Martino	Surabaya State University
Aksin, Nur	Semarang State University
Eka, Vebriani Safitry; Yesika Kristin; Gatri	Jakarta State University

Tuti, Selly Filanda; Ennike Rahayu Lestari; Gustinawati Gustinawati; Retnowati WD	Semarang State University
Nurhayati, Edward Jumadi Tandiarang	Muhammadiyah University of Makassar
Fatmawati, Rifqi Muhammad; Nur Lailatul	Muhammadiyah University Prof Dr Hamka
Permana, Ri Sabti Septarini; Rohmat Taufik; Nofitri Heriyani; Ray Tri	Muhammadiyah University of Tangerang
Unengkari, Marti Dewi	Garut University
Trisnadi, Dedy; Hengki, Salmi; Puspita, Jezzy Dela	Mercu Buana University
Setiowati, Hilman Abu Dzarrin, Kholid Fathoni, Yuliana	Muhammad Arsyad Al Banjari Islamic University of Kalimantan
Rini, Ruharini	Bina Sarana Informatics University
Wahyunie, Goddess	Tarumanagara University
Sari, Fitria; Sadiq, Teuku Fajar	Sheikh Yusuf Islamic University
Maghreb Imam; Dewi Tuti Muryati; Supriyadi	Semarang University
Margono, Pramono	UBS
Saputri Humaira, Marheni Eka; Qur'an	Langlangbuana University
Yuliani, Irma	Batanghari University
Sari, Novita	university Of islam
Sinaga, Syarifah	Indonesian Islamic University
Sormin, Jessica Puji Astuti; Partogians; Sianggaran, Addella Addella; Rosdiana	Atma Jaya Indonesian Catholic University
Petrus Hasudungan Sitinjak; Ruzikna; Tamba, Lena Farida; Hot Dame	Riau University
Ndruru Taronisokhi, Eferoni; Zebua	Indonesian Methodist University
Pricilla, Irma Sari Octaviani; Lidya; Ulyanti, Edi	Pamulang University
Wulandari, Ratna	Tamansiswa Bachelor University
Suhardiyah, Martha	PGRI Adi Buana University
Supriyatno, Saparuddin Siregar, Nurlaila, Anggun	ITB AAS INDONESIA Surakarta
Nurwati, Dede Muladi, Nurwati; Widyastuti, Sri	ITB Ahmad Dahlan Jakarta
Wijaksana, Tri Indra	IIB Darmajaya
Rohana, Aliah Pratiwi; Siti	STIE PGRI Dewantara Jombang

Doloksaribu, Nora Anisa Br Sinulingga; Winda Sri Astuti	Institute Of Computer Science (IOCS)
Zuhdi Miftahudin Abdul, Saefudin; Student	Unitary Business and Informatics Institute
Riandi, Irwan Kurniawan; Rest	Pelita Indonesia Institute of Business and Technology
Silalahi, Mitha Christina Ginting; Kristina	Medan College of Economics-LMII
Bachtiar, Riska Fitriani; Christian PW Hutasoit; Maryati	Student Online Journal (JOM)
Marisa, Nia; Kopakanti, Desinta Bio; Mutia, Nur	Collection of Law Faculty Journals
Harahap, Triyani Sartika; Widiawati, Helena Anggreini; Saputra, Eddy	Premise Law Journal
S Udana, Lina Marlina; Stefia, Retired Hardiyanto; Cheryl Marlitta	Syntax Corporation Indonesia
Kartika, Mira Gayatri	Kresna Bina Prima Humans
Pratama Samingun, Angga Wahyu, Handoyo	Statistics Student Journal
Santika, Goddess	Mabis
Rialmi Papang, Zackharia; Patoni	Institute for Democracy and Community Empowerment Studies (LKD-PM)
Ghalba Harimukti, Firdaus; Wandebori	The Indonesian Journal of Business Administration
Sendidevi, Ida Ayu Wayan Meryawira	IUS Journal
Miswanto, Wardayani Wardayani; Miswanto	Civitas: Journal of Management Studies
Gana, Stefanus Don Rade; Dhey W Tadeus; Gana	Green Publishers
Eli Purwanti	Economics
Sangkala's son, Riduansyah; Ruslan	Publisher Dynasty

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

4.2. Bibliometric Mapping of CIMB Niaga Sharia and Conventional Banks

Based on research articles obtained from search results on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garb a) which are exported into RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using software VOSViewer, the results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps regarding Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah and Conventional

Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

The results of the co-word network map of research developments regarding Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah and Conventional are divided into 8 clusters and 116 topics, namely as follows:

- Cluster 1, red consists of 34 topics, namely: ability, analysis, career development, commitment, company, corporate image, cost, customer, customer loyalty, customer satisfaction, employee, employee performance, independent variable, influence, intensity, loyalty, motivation, multiple regression, organizational commitment, organizational culture, organizational learning, performance, promotion, questionnaire, research, sales force, service quality, significant effect, spss, t table, theory, value.
- Cluster 2, green consists of 20 topics, namely: assets, capital, car, equity, financial performance, financial ratio, good corporate governance, idr, loan, margin, net profit margin, npm, pt bank Cimb Niaga Tbk, ratio, return, regc, roa, roe, significant difference terms.
- Cluster 3, blue, consists of 19 topics, namely: accede, appraisal, assessment report, bank niaga, bankruptcy, bpr, cimb commerce auto financial, collateral, credit, debtor, education sector, implementation, fiduciary guarantee, credit, la, research method, third part y.
- Cluster 4, yellow consists of 15 topics, namely: access, bank, bank secrecy, banking, banking service, CIMB Niaga, CIMB Niaga Syariah, development, fiduciary principle, interest, management, process, profit, strategy, system.
- Cluster 5, purple consists of 13 topics, namely: Bank Cimb Niaga, Bank Cimb Niaga Syariah, comparison, conflict management, data envelope analysis,

efficiency, independent sample t test, performance, financial performance, organization, company, total assets, variables.

- Cluster 6, light blue, consists of 12 topics, namely: credit restructuring, data analysis technique, debt, der, difference, equity ratio, micro credit, performing loan, purposive sampling, risk, sampling technique, secondary data.
- Cluster 7, orange consists of 2 topics, namely: fees, income.
- Cluster 8, brown consists of 1 topic, namely: company.

4.3. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Problems at CIMB Niaga Sharia and Conventional Banks

Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 11 problems that occur at Bank CIMB Niaga, namely:

First, Fast-Fourier transformation modeling on corporate bond valuation. Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is a mathematical transformation method that can be used to process signals quickly. In the context of corporate bond valuation at CIMB Niaga bank, FFT can be used to identify patterns in historical bond market data and produce estimates of the future value of bonds. One of the main applications of FFT in corporate bond valuation is yield curve analysis. Yield curve is a graph that shows the relationship between interest rates and terms for bonds of the same credit quality. By applying FFT to the yield curve, CIMB Niaga bank can identify patterns that appear in historical yield curve data and produce estimates of future yield curves. This can help CIMB Niaga bank make more accurate investment decisions. In addition, FFT can also be used to identify fluctuations in historical bond price data. By modeling bond price fluctuations using FFT, CIMB Niaga bank can produce estimates of future bond prices, which can assist in making decisions about buying and selling bonds.

Second, CAMEL analysis to assess bank health. CAMEL analysis is a bank health assessment framework that consists of five key factors: capital adequacy (adequacy), asset quality, management, earnings and liquidity. Let's apply this assessment framework to Bank CIMB Niaga:

- (1) Capital Adequacy is an important indicator for assessing a bank's ability to bear the credit risks it takes. Bank CIMB Niaga has a fairly strong capital adequacy ratio, with a Total Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) of 22.0% as of September 2022, which is well above the minimum limit set by the regulator.
- (2) Asset Quality, which reflects the health of the bank's credit portfolio, and can be measured through the Non-Performing Loan (NPL) ratio. CIMB Niaga has an NPL ratio of 2.2% as of September 2022, which is relatively stable compared to the previous year. However, this bank needs to still pay attention to the quality of its assets so that it is not exposed to too much credit risk.

- (3) Management is the key to success in running bank operations well and healthily. CIMB Niaga has demonstrated a strong commitment to good management, by adopting best practices in risk management and operations.
- (4) Earnings, which is a measure of a bank's financial performance and can be measured through the Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) ratios. CIMB Niaga has recorded an ROA of 1.4% and an ROE of 11.8% as of September 2022, which shows quite good financial performance.
- (5) Liquidity, namely the bank's ability to fulfill short-term financial obligations and can be measured through the Loan to Deposit ratio (LDR) and Cash Ratio (CR). CIMB Niaga has an LDR of 93.7% as of September 2022, which indicates a fairly high level of liquidity.

Third, collaborate with the Public Appraisal Service/KJPP in assessing home ownership credit collateral. The cooperation mechanism between CIMB Niaga Bank and the Public Appraisal Service/KJPP in assessing home ownership credit collateral is as follows: (1) CIMB Niaga Bank will provide data and information regarding property objects that will be used as credit collateral to the Public Appraisal Service/KJPP. This data includes information regarding location, property type, land and building size, and condition of the property. (2) Public Appraisal Services/KJPP will check and survey the property. This is done to obtain further information regarding the condition of the property, including the physical condition, legality and market value of the property. (3) After conducting the survey, the Public Appraisal Service/KJPP will prepare an appraisal report containing the market value of the property. The report will contain information regarding the market value of the property used as credit collateral. (4) The assessment report will be submitted to CIMB Niaga Bank, which will then be used as a reference in determining the amount of credit that can be given to customers.

Fourth, the best model for forecasting closing stock data uses the ARCH-GARCH method. To create a forecasting model using the ARCH-GARCH method on Bank CIMB Niaga shares, the steps that can be taken include the following: (1) Data collection: Collect Bank CIMB Niaga share price data over a certain time period. This data can be obtained from various sources, such as financial websites or software applications that collect real-time stock price data. (2) Data analysis: Carry out data analysis to understand the patterns and trends in Bank CIMB Niaga's share prices over a predetermined time period. This can be done using stock price charts or technical indicators such as moving averages, MACD, or RSI. (3) Estimation of ARCH-GARCH model: Estimate the ARCH-GARCH model using statistical software, such as EViews or Stata. This model will provide an estimate of Bank CIMB Niaga's share price volatility, so it can be used to improve forecasting results. (4) Model validation: Validate the model to ensure that it is suitable for use in forecasting. This can be done using evaluation metrics, such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE) or Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). (5) Forecasting: Use the adjusted ARCH-GARCH model to forecast the future share price of Bank CIMB Niaga. This can be done using statistical or spreadsheet software such as Microsoft Excel.

Fifth, factors that influence the realization of micro credit. There are several factors that can influence the realization of micro credit at CIMB Niaga Bank, including: (1) Customer character or profile: this factor is related to the Bank's trust in the customer's character, such as a good credit history, discipline in paying bills, and ability to manage business. The better the customer's character, the higher the possibility that the microcredit will be realized. (2) Customer capacity: this factor is related to the customer's ability to fulfill credit payment obligations. The bank will assess the customer's capacity based on business income or the business being run. The greater the customer's capacity, the higher the possibility that the microcredit will be realized. (3) Conditions of the customer's business or business: this factor is related to the conditions of the business or business run by the customer. The bank will assess the customer's business potential based on the business sector being run, business location and market potential. The better the customer's business or business conditions, the higher the possibility that the microcredit will be realized. (4) Collateral or guarantee: this factor is related to the type and value of collateral or guarantee provided by the customer. The greater the value of the collateral or guarantee, the higher the possibility that the microcredit will be realized. (5) Bank policies and requirements: this factor is related to the policies and requirements set by the Bank. For example, document requirements that must be met by customers, interest amount, credit tenor, and so on. If customers can fulfill the Bank's requirements and policies, the possibility that microcredit will be realized is greater.

Sixth, conflict management between ex-Bank Lippo and ex-Bank Niaga after the merger. Conflict management between two merging organizations (in this case the merger between Bank Lippo and Bank Niaga) is a significant challenge in corporate mergers. The following are several steps that can be taken in managing post-merger conflicts: (1) Form a special management team to handle conflicts: This team should consist of members from both banks, who have expertise in conflict management and communication. They must have the ability to identify problems, develop solutions, and monitor their implementation. (2) Communicate a clear vision and mission. A clear vision and mission will help employees from both banks understand the company's direction and create a common culture. Open and honest communication will allow employees to feel valued and involved in decisions that impact their work. (3) Hold small group meetings and discussions: Small group meetings and discussions can help to open channels of communication between employees of both banks. This can provide an opportunity for employees to talk about concerns they have and feel heard. (4) Maintain fair and consistent policies and procedures: Creating fair and consistent policies and procedures will help eliminate disparities in treatment and prevent conflicts. These policies and procedures must be applied consistently and transparently throughout the company. (5) Provide training and development to employees: Training and development can help employees to acquire the skills necessary to resolve problems and conflicts. This can also help build a company culture of mutual support and collaboration. (6) Measuring and monitoring performance: Measuring and monitoring performance will help know

whether the implemented solution is effective. If it is not effective, the company can develop an improvement plan or other strategy to resolve the conflict.

Seventh, the effectiveness of internal control in compliance with accounting rules against the tendency of accounting fraud. Several steps that Bank CIMB Niaga or other financial institutions can take to improve internal control and compliance with accounting rules include: (1) Developing and implementing strict policies and procedures to manage financial transactions, such as clear verification, validation and authorization processes; (2) Ensure that financial reporting is accurate and timely by implementing correct accounting practices and following applicable accounting standards; (3) Implement strict supervision and monitoring of financial transactions to identify suspicious activities and prevent fraud; (4) Conduct regular internal and external audits to evaluate the effectiveness of internal control and ensure compliance with accounting rules; (5) Conduct ongoing training and education to increase awareness and understanding of internal control and compliance with accounting rules throughout the organization.

Eighth, the influence of Electronic Banking transactions on Fee Based Income. The influence of Electronic Banking transactions on Fee Based Income at CIMB Niaga Bank can be influenced by several factors such as the use of e-banking services by customers, the type of transactions carried out, and the fees charged by the bank for using these services. The increasing use of e-banking services can increase fees CIMB Niaga Bank Based Income because the bank can collect fees for every transaction carried out by customers through this service. Apart from that, the type of transaction carried out can also affect Fee Based Income, for example transactions that use additional features such as transfers to other bank accounts, bill payments, product purchases, etc., can result in additional fees charged by the bank. However, banks must also consider the costs incurred for developing and maintaining e-banking services. If these costs are higher than the income generated, then the impact on Fee Based Income can be negative. Apart from that, competition from other banks that also offer similar e-banking services could affect the influence of Electronic Banking transactions on Fee Based Income at Bank CIMB Niaga. If another bank offers lower fees or better service, then customers can switch to another bank and affect Bank CIMB Niaga's Fee Based Income.

Ninth, legal protection for creditors in relation to bankruptcy applications submitted by debtors. A bankruptcy petition is a legal effort made by the debtor (the party who has the obligation to pay debts) to ask the court to decide that he is insolvent (bankrupt) and put him in insolvent status (unable to pay debts). In this case, creditors (parties who own receivables) obtain legal protection in several ways, especially through Law Number 37 of 2004 concerning Bankruptcy and Suspension of Debt Payment Obligations (UU KPKPU). The following are some of the things that the law protects creditors:

- (1) Right to File a Bankruptcy Petition: Creditors have the right to file a bankruptcy petition against debtors who have not been able to pay their debts.

In this case, the creditor can submit a bankruptcy petition to the local Commercial Court where the debtor is domiciled.

- (2) **Right to Debt Payment:** In the bankruptcy process, creditors have the right to obtain payment from the debtor's assets imposed by the Commercial Court. This aims to ensure that creditors can obtain part or all of the debt that has not been paid by the debtor.
- (3) **Protection against Transfer of Debtor's Assets:** The KPKPU Law provides protection against unauthorized transfer of debtor's assets. In this case, the transfer of the debtor's assets carried out within a certain time before the bankruptcy petition is filed can be declared invalid by the Commercial Court.
- (4) **Protection against Inquest Action:** In the bankruptcy process, the Commercial Court can carry out an inquest action to find out all of the debtor's assets and debts. However, creditors have protection against such inquest actions because these actions must be carried out while respecting the creditors' rights.
- (5) **Right to Supervise Bankruptcy Procedures:** Creditors also have the right to supervise ongoing bankruptcy procedures. In this case, creditors can monitor decision making and ensure that their rights are protected during the bankruptcy process.

Tenth, the influence of the number of card sales representatives and the intensity of promotional programs on credit card sales volume. The influence of the number of card sales representatives and the intensity of promotional programs on credit card sales volume at Bank CIMB Niaga can vary depending on various factors, such as target market, competitor position, economic conditions and the bank's internal policies. However, in general, the number of cards More sales representatives can expand marketing reach and provide more opportunities to sell credit cards to potential customers. This can help increase the volume of credit card sales at Bank CIMB Niaga. Meanwhile, the intensity of promotional programs can also play an important role in increasing customer awareness about the credit card products offered by Bank CIMB Niaga. By carrying out appropriate and effective promotions, banks can attract potential customers to buy their credit cards, and thereby increase sales volume.

Eleventh, the influence of independence, competence and professionalism of internal auditors on the ability to detect fraud, namely:

- (1) **Internal Auditor Independence.** Independence is the ability of internal auditors to carry out their duties objectively and not be influenced by other parties. In this case, independence is very important in ensuring that internal auditors can carry out their work neutrally and free from pressure from parties involved in bank operations. If internal auditors have strong independence, they will be better able to find indications of fraud at Bank CIMB Niaga. This is because they can carry out their duties objectively, without any influence from any party. Conversely, if the independence of

internal auditors is weak, they may not be able to conduct effective audits and may ignore signs of fraud occurring.

- (2) **Internal Auditor Competency.** Competency is the ability and knowledge possessed by internal auditors in carrying out their duties. A competent internal auditor has a deep understanding of auditing and can understand the risk of fraud at Bank CIMB Niaga. They can identify security gaps and rule violations that could allow fraud to occur. If internal auditors have strong competence, they will be able to strengthen Bank CIMB Niaga's internal control system and increase their ability to detect signs of fraud occurring. On the other hand, if the competence of internal auditors is weak, they may not be able to carry out effective audits and cannot identify indications of fraud at Bank CIMB Niaga.
- (3) **Internal Auditor Professionalism.** Professionalism is the attitude and behavior of internal auditors in carrying out their duties. A professional internal auditor will hold high standards of ethics and professionalism in carrying out his duties. They can communicate well with audit team members and related parties at Bank CIMB Niaga to identify and follow up on indications of fraud. If internal auditors have high professionalism, they will be able to identify signs of fraud at CIMB Niaga Bank and provide objective and detailed reports about indications of fraud. On the other hand, if the professionalism of internal auditors is weak, they may not be able to reveal indications of fraud properly and make reports that are inaccurate or incomplete.

4.4. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank CIMB Niaga Sharia and Conventional Performance

The first finding, based on a Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, is that there are 5 comparisons of Bank CIMB Niaga's performance with other banks, namely: (1) Debt to Equity Ratio / DER with Bank Mega; (2) Efficiency of credit distribution with Bank Mega Syariah; (3) Financial performance, including Return On Assets / ROA, Return On Equity / ROE, Loan to Deposit Ratio / LDR, Operational Costs to Operational Income / BOPO with Bank Rakyat Indonesia / BRI, Bank Mandiri, Bank Central Asia / BCA, Bank OCBC NISP; (4) Degree of Financial Leverage with Bank Danamon; and (5) Profit and interest sharing system with Bank Muamalat Indonesia.

The second finding, based on a Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, is that there are 5 Bank CIMB Niaga products, namely: (1) Multi-service Ijarah Agreement in the education sector at Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah; (2) Payment system via CIMB Niaga mobile account; (3) Micro working capital credit to Small and Medium Enterprises/SMEs; (4) Murabahah bil Wakalah agreement with sharia analysis; and (5) Home Ownership Financing/PKR Murabahah.

The third finding, based on a Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, is that there are 16 CIMB Niaga Bank performance reports,

namely: (1) Return On Assets / ROA; (2) Return On Equity /ROE; (3) Gross Profit Margin /GPM; (4) Net Profit Margin /NPM; (5) Operating Profit Margin /OPM; (6) Total Debts to Equity; (7) Interest Coverage Ratio; (8) Debt Ratio; (9) Earnings Per Share /EPS; (10) Risk Management of the Mudharabah Financing; (11) Liquidity Ratios, including: Quick Ratio, Investing Policy Ratio, Banking Ratio, Assets to Loans Ratio, Investment Portfolio Ratio, Cash Ratio, Loan to Deposit Ratio /LDR; (12) Solvency Ratios, including: Primary Ratio, Risk Assets Ratio, Secondary Risk Ratio, Capital Ratio, Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR; (13) Profitability Ratios, including: Rate Return on Loans, Interest Margin on Earning Assets, Financial Leverage Multiplier /FLM, Assets Utilization, Interest Expense Ratio, Cost of Fund, Cost of Money, Cost of Loanable Fund, Cost of Operable Fund, Cost of Efficiency; (14) Good Corporate Governance /GCG; (15) Total Asset Turnover /TATO; and (16) Capital adequacy.

The fourth finding, based on a Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 15 employee/Human Resource performances at Bank CIMB Niaga, namely: (1) Competence; (2) Organizational commitment; (3) Career development; (4) Termination of employment/layoff due to force majeure; (5) Outsourced worker wage system; (6) Management of static debtor archives in the Loan Workout Division; (7) Gender roles; (8) Organizational Citizenship Behavior; (9) Organizational culture; (10) Internal Marketing; (11) Company orientation; (12) Organizational security; (13) Compensation; (14) Motivation; and (15) Discipline.

The fifth finding, based on a Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 17 determinants of customer interest and satisfaction in transactions at Bank CIMB Niaga, namely: (1) Service quality; (2) Product quality; (3) Trust; (4) Commitment; (5) Bank image; (6) Complaint Handling; (7) Service Recovery; (8) Convenience; (9) Promotion; (10) Friendliness; (11) Trust; (12) Religiosity; (13) Income; (14) Television and print media advertisements; (15) Marketing mix; (16) Risk perception; and (17) Branchless Banking.

The sixth finding, based on a Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, is that there are 8 customer problems at Bank CIMB Niaga, namely: (1) Judicial review of unilateral blocking of customer accounts; (2) Juridical review of fiduciary guarantees related to bad credit at CIMB Niaga Auto Finance; (3) Protection of customer data at Bank CIMB Niaga KC Medan; (4) Destruction of fiduciary collateral objects in financing at CIMB Niaga Auto Finance Medan Branch; (5) Restructuring of problem loans; (6) Settlement of bad credit during the Covid-19 pandemic; (7) Settlement of bad credit on unsecured credit; and (8) The influence of Switching Costs on inertia and calculative commitment.

The seventh finding, based on a Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 10 innovations carried out by CIMB Niaga Bank, namely: (1) Marketing strategy for fund raising/ funding products; (2) Management Information Systems/SIM includes: data, people, SIM activities, telecommunications networks, computer technology; (3) Strategy to increase the growth of Debitu Small Medium Enterprise; (4) Management audit for effectiveness and efficiency of the marketing function; (5) Support system for assessing the eligibility of credit financing

recipients; (6) Implementation of Green Building in an effort to efficiency operational costs; (7) Promotional applications using Mobile Augmented Reality; (8) Media relations strategy; (9) Application of the Nearest Neighbor Algorithm in predicting the feasibility of accepting credit cards; and (10) Company business strategy proposal.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah and Conventional during the period 201 to 2022 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 99 research articles, which come from national journals indexed by Sinta.
- The affiliate/institution that publishes the most research results is the FEB Brawijaya University Student Scientific Journal, which is the publisher of the most journals, with 8 articles.
- In the mapping visualization using VOSviewer, research developments regarding Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah and Conventional are divided into 8 clusters and 116 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 34 topics, cluster 2 consists of 20 topics, cluster 3 consists of 19 topics, cluster 4 consists of 15 topics, cluster 5 consists of 13 topics, and cluster 6 consists of 12 topics, cluster 7 consists of 2 topics, and cluster 8 consists of 1 topic.
- Based on the Library Research, there are 8 main research themes, namely: (1) Problems at Bank CIMB Niaga with 11 findings; (2) Comparison of the Bank's performance with other banks; (3) Bank Products; (4) Bank performance reports; (5) Employee performance/Human Resources; (6) Determinants of customer interest and satisfaction in transactions; (7) Customer problems; and (8) Innovation carried out by the Bank.

REFERENCES

- , P. H., Utami, S. B., & Karlina, N. (2022). Analisis Bibliometrik: Perkembangan Penelitian Dan Publikasi Mengenai Koordinasi Program Menggunakan Vosviewer. *Jurnal Pustaka Budaya*, 9(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.31849/pb.v9i1.8599>
- Aulia, E. S., & Rusli, R. P. (2020). Manfaat Kajian Bibliometrik Sebagai Penunjang Analisis Kebutuhan Kurikulum Program Studi Ilmu Perpustakaan dan Informasi. *Inovasi Kurikulum*, 17(2), 59–68. <https://doi.org/10.17509/jik.v17i2.36827>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, Vol 7, No 1 (2022), 43–68. <https://journal.iainlangsa.ac.id/index.php/ebis/article/view/3895/2011>
- Fatmawati, R. M. N. L. (2020). IMPLEMENTASI AKAD IJARAH MULTIJASA SEKTOR PENDIDIKAN: STUDI KASUS BANK CIMB NIAGA SYARIAH. *Ekonomi Islam*, Vol. 11 No. 2 (2020): *Jurnal Ekonomi Islam Fakultas Agama Islam*

- UHAMKA, 187–204.
<https://journal.uhamka.ac.id/index.php/jei/article/view/4802/2030>
- Janrosl, V. S. E. (2019). PENGARUH KEEFEKTIFAN PENGENDALIAN INTERNAL KETAATAN ATURAN AKUNTANSI TERHADAP KECENDERUNGAN KECURANGAN AKUNTANSI PADA BANK CIMB NIAGA. *JOURNAL OF APPLIED MANAGERIAL ACCOUNTING*, Vol 3 No 2 (2019): *JOURNAL OF APPLIED MANAGERIAL ACCOUNTING*, 159–167.
<https://jurnal.polibatam.ac.id/index.php/JAMA/article/view/1577/882>
- Lestari. (2021). *Pengaruh Diferensiasi, Financial Literacy, dan Service fitur terhadap Minat Nasabah menggunakan kartu kredit syariah.*
- Rialmi Papang, Z. P. (2020). Pengaruh Pengembangan Karir terhadap Kinerja Karyawan pada PT Bank CIMB Niaga Cabang Pondok Indah, Jakarta Selatan. *Jurnal Mandiri : Ilmu Pengetahuan, Seni, Dan Teknologi*, Vol 4 No 2: Desember 2020, 210–221.
<http://jurnalmandiri.com/index.php/mandiri/article/view/129/94>
- Silalahi, M. C. G. K. (2020). ANALISIS PERBEDAAN KINERJA KEUANGAN PERUSAHAAN SEBELUM DAN SETELAH MERGER (Studi pada Bank CIMB Niaga yang Terdaftar di BEI). *JURNAL MANAJEMEN, Jurnal Manajemen Volume 6 Nomor 1 (2020)*, 35–46.
<http://ejournal.lmiimedan.net/index.php/jm/article/view/95/83>
- Sudana Lina, S. M. (2019). PENGARUH KECUKUPAN MODAL DAN EFISIENSI OPERASIONAL TERHADAP PROFITABILITAS PADA BANK CIMB NIAGA SYARIAH. *Syntax Literate, Jurnal Ilmiah Indonesia*, Vol 4 No 1 (2019): *Syntax Literate*. <https://jurnal.syntaxliterate.co.id/index.php/syntax-literate/article/view/545/830>
- Supriasmono, R. (2020). *PENGARUH TRUST, COOPERATION, COMMITMENT DAN COMMUNICATION TERHADAP KEPUASAN NASABAH PENGGUNA KARTU KREDIT BANK NIAGA Oleh R.Supriasmono*. 14.
- Ulhaq, Z. S., & Rahmayanti. (2020). Panduan Penulisan Skripsi Literatur Review. In *Fakultas Kedokteran dan Ilmu Kesehatan Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang* (Vol. 53, Issue 9).
- Yuliani, I. (2022). Analisis Faktor yang Mempengaruhi Minat Nasabah Memilih Produk Tabungan Wakaf di Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah Cabang Samarinda. *Ekonomis: Journal of Economics and Business*, Vol 6, No 1 (2022): Maret, 183–189.
<http://ekonomis.unbari.ac.id/index.php/ojsekonomis/article/view/497/248>